

ARCHITECTURE

THE ROLE OF METAPHORS IN SHAPING THE ARTISTIC IMAGE OF AN ARCHITECTURAL STRUCTURE

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Abstract

Architecture, as a form of art, often employs metaphors to convey deeper meaning and interconnectedness with cultural and historical contexts. Metaphors in architecture not only decorate, but also serve as a bridge between the material world and the world of ideas, giving buildings symbolic significance and deepening the perception of space, for a deep symbolic interpretation of buildings and structures. Through the metaphorical use of forms and materials, architects convey hidden meanings and cultural characteristics, which contributes to the creation of a unique artistic image.

Keywords: architecture, metaphor, artistic image, symbolism, cultural significance.

Introduction

Architectural structures often utilize metaphors to interact with their audience on a subconscious level. This allows architecture to transcend its functional purpose and acquire profound symbolic and aesthetic meanings. Examining the role of metaphors in shaping architectural imagery provides a deeper understanding of the influence of culture and traditions on architectural design. In the realm of architecture, metaphors serve as a powerful tool for conveying complex meanings and emotions through visual representation and design. Metaphor is a means of expanding the creative freedom of the author in constructing the image of an architectural object [1].

Metaphors in architecture can manifest themselves in various forms, such as the use of certain forms, materials, or structural elements that imitate natural objects or cultural symbols. The properties that the architect has incorporated into the work should be read by the viewer.

That is, there is a certain connection between the architect and the viewer, which consists in the author's prediction of the viewer's psychological reaction to the work of architecture [2]. For example, the Parliament building in Budapest, the Hungarian National Assembly, is one of the most impressive examples of Neo-Gothic architecture in the world. The Parliament building in Budapest, designed in the Neo-Gothic style by architect Imre Steindl and completed in 1904, serves as a striking example of the use of metaphor in architecture. It symbolizes the "light of democracy" through its

sharp Gothic towers and magnificent stained-glass windows that let in light, creating an atmosphere of openness and transparency. These elements not only decorate the building, but also emphasize the importance of democratic values, making political openness visually tangible. The interior space also reflects this metaphor: spacious and bright halls visually emphasize accessibility and openness. This symbolizes Hungary's desire to demonstrate its commitment to democratic principles and contribute to European political life.

Moving to another continent, the Sydney Opera House, designed by Jørn Utzon and opened in 1973, continues this theme of symbolism in architecture, but with a different emphasis. The building's shape, resembling sails, reflects Australia's maritime past and its seafaring traditions. These "sails" are not just architectural elements; they are a metaphor for the pursuit of new discoveries and opportunities, emphasizing both the cultural and scientific and technological development of the country. Utzon used this form to link the historical past with the nation's modern pursuit of innovation, making the Sydney Opera House not only a cultural center that reflects history but also a symbol of the spirit, optimism, and the nation's striving for new discoveries and opportunities.

Sails are also a symbol of technological progress and innovation, emphasizing Australia's desire to be at the forefront of modernity and technology. This metaphor emphasizes both cultural and scientific and technological development, making the Sydney Opera House a significant symbol of national spirit and optimism (Pic.1).

Pic.1 Images of the Opera House from the books by Charlesa Jenksa

The same look to the future with a bias towards the past is presented in the project of the Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao, designed by Frank Gehry, which is an example of deconstructivist architecture and is often described as one of the greatest architectural works of our time. The museum's exterior, resembling a ship, not only refers to the city's industrial heritage, historically linked to shipbuilding, but also symbolizes the reinterpretation of this heritage in a modern context.

The museum's form also symbolizes the renewal and reinterpretation of the city's industrial heritage. The building's shiny titanium panels reflect the waters of the Nervión River, creating a visual interaction between the museum and its surroundings. This emphasizes the link between Bilbao's past and present, where new cultural venues like the museum stimulate the city's social and economic revival (Pic.2).

Pic. 2 The Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao.

These examples demonstrate how metaphors in architecture can deepen the perception of buildings, transforming them into symbols of cultural, historical, and technological aspects of society. Through such metaphors, architectural objects acquire not only functional but also symbolic significance, contributing to the formation of a unique identity and cultural image of the people.

Metaphors in architecture are not just decorative elements, they embody deep symbolic meanings and reflect social moods and historical contexts.

“It is no less obvious that in every program, however complex it may be, there is a dominant idea. Basic needs require appropriate artistic forms, and, consequently, decoration that reveals these forms” [3].

Through the use of metaphors, buildings can communicate with us, conveying complex ideas and emotions. These symbols and images in architecture help people to see familiar concepts in a new way, to rethink them and to see a broader perspective. Metaphors give buildings character, making them memorable and meaningful. They can express the aspirations of a nation, its cultural characteristics, technological achievements, or historical connection with certain symbols and elements.

Architectural metaphors operate on a subconscious level, evoking certain associations and emotions in the viewer. This is especially important in the creation of public spaces, where architecture serves not only as shelter, but also as a means of interacting with culture and history. In this context, architectural structures

become not just objects of observation, but also active participants in cultural dialogue.

The conscious use of Z10 in Z4 emphasizes the role of the Z3 not only as an Z8, but also as an Z2 and Z9, who shapes the spatial environment in such a way that it speaks to us, telling stories, raising important questions and inspiring reflection.

Comparative analysis of metaphors in architecture, literature and painting

Metaphors, being a powerful means of expression in art, are used to convey complex concepts through more accessible or familiar images. In architecture, literature and painting, metaphors serve not only as decoration, but also as a profound means of communication, influencing the emotional and intellectual perception of the audience.

In architecture, metaphors can be embodied physically through form, space and materials. They are used to create symbolic or emotional impressions on the viewer. For example, the U.S. Supreme Court building, designed in the neoclassical style, symbolizes stability, order, and eternity, which emphasizes the importance and seriousness of the functions performed in it. Metaphors in architecture help viewers associate the building with certain ideas and values, which enhances its perception and understanding.

In literature, metaphors are often used to describe and convey the emotions, ideas, and experiences of characters. For example, in Gabriel Garcia Marquez's novel 'One Hundred Years of Solitude,' the metaphor of the eternal struggle with loneliness experienced by each character emphasizes the universal theme of human isolation and its impact on an individual's life. Metaphors in literature enrich the text, providing the reader with a deeper level of interpretation and interaction with the work.

In painting, metaphors are conveyed through color, form, and composition. In the works of artists such as Salvador Dali, metaphors serve to create surreal images that evoke strong associations and emotional responses in the viewer. For example, in the painting "The Persistence of Memory," the melting clocks in a desolate landscape can symbolize the relativity of time and its fleeting nature.

Comparing metaphors in these three art forms, one can see how they adapt to their mediums to achieve the desired effect. All three art forms use metaphors to provide the audience with a deeper understanding of the subject or theme, but each form does so through its unique expressive means. Architecture does this in a spatial and physical context, literature uses words to create mental and emotional images, and painting appeals to visual perception and aesthetic senses.

This comparison highlights the significance of metaphors as a bridge between the inner world of the creator and the outer world of the audience, allowing for a better understanding of how different art forms interact with the cultural and individual contexts of their perception.

Metaphors in architecture can be deeply understood by applying the theoretical approaches of semiotics, the science that studies signs and symbols in communication processes. Semiotics in architecture analyzes how buildings and their elements function as sign systems, conveying various meanings and messages.

Venturi prefers decorated sheds because, he argues, they are capable of more effective communication, and modern architects have been designing only "ducks" for too long. In terms of semiotics, the "duck" is an iconic sign, as the signifier (form) has some common aspects with the signified (content). The decorated mansion depends on acquired values — inscriptions or decorations that are symbolic signs (Pic.3).

Pic 3. Robert Venturi "Duck" vs. Decorated Shed

Semiotics, founded by Charles Sanders Peirce and further developed by Roland Barthes, Umberto Eco, and others, offers a framework for analyzing symbols and signs in culture. In the context of architecture, every element of a building (form, material, location) can be interpreted as a sign that carries certain cultural, social, or personal meanings.

Peirce distinguished three components of a sign: the representamen (the sign itself), the object (what the sign stands for), and the interpretant (the meaning of the sign for the interpreter).[4]. In architecture, for example, masonry can symbolize stability and durability (object), while for the observer (interpretant) it can evoke associations with reliability or traditionality (Pic.4).

Pic. 4 Peirce's Triadic Model of the Sign

Roland Barthes, in his work, distinguished between denotation (the literal meaning of a sign) and connotation (the associative, cultural meaning). In architecture, the denotative level can represent simply the physical structure, while the connotative level can embody power, innovation, or other abstract concepts. For example, glass facades of buildings can denote modern construction technologies, however, connotatively they can symbolize transparency and openness of the organization.

Using semiotic analysis, architects and critics can unravel how various elements of buildings influence people's perception and behavior. For example, ceiling height can influence perceptions of freedom or oppression; wide, open spaces can evoke feelings of community or vulnerability depending on the context.

The semiotic approach also emphasizes the importance of cultural context in the interpretation of architectural signs. What may be considered a symbol of luxury and power in one culture may not carry the same meaning in another. This cultural variability requires architects to be mindful in their use of symbols to avoid misunderstandings and conflicts.

The influence of cultural differences on the interpretation of metaphors in architecture

Architecture, like other art forms, is deeply rooted in cultural traditions and contexts, which influence how metaphors are perceived and interpreted by different

cultures. Exploring cultural differences in the interpretation of metaphors can help architects and designers create more meaningful and resonant projects in different regions of the world.

Every culture has unique symbols and meanings that can be embodied in architecture. For example, in China, the color red is traditionally associated with good luck and joy, so it can often be seen in the decoration of buildings, especially during holidays and celebrations. In Western cultures, the color red can have other connotations, including danger or passion.

The shapes and styles of buildings are also interpreted differently depending on cultural contexts. Gothic architecture with its pointed arches and tall towers can be perceived in Europe as a symbol of medieval Christian spirituality, while in other regions the same architectural elements can be perceived as alien or exotic.

Cultural differences are also manifested in the adaptation of architectural designs to local conditions and traditions. For example, in the hot climates of the Persian Gulf countries, traditional architecture uses elements such as wind towers and thick walls for passive cooling of buildings. These elements carry not only a functional load, but also metaphorically reflect local strategies for adapting to harsh environmental conditions (Pic.5).

Pic. 5 The Basic Equations for Regional Architecture in Saudi Arabia

Concepts of space and privacy vary greatly between cultures, which influences architectural design. American or European architecture values open space and large windows for maximum interaction with the outside world. In more conservative cultures, such as in some Islamic countries, preferences may shift towards

more closed and protected spaces, reflecting stricter notions of personal life and privacy.

For effective interaction with local cultural contexts, architects and designers need to study cultural characteristics and work closely with local specialists

and communities. This allows for the creation of architectural projects that not only take into account local cultural characteristics but also contribute to cultural exchange and understanding.

Conclusions

Metaphors in architecture have a significant impact on the formation of the artistic image and cultural value of architectural structures. They contribute to a deep symbolic interpretation of buildings, giving them not only functional, but also aesthetic and emotional significance. Using metaphors, architects convey hidden meanings, referring to cultural, historical and social contexts, which allows buildings to communicate with the audience on a deeper, subconscious level.

Through the metaphorical use of forms, materials and structural elements, architectural objects acquire symbolic significance, becoming not just objects of observation, but active participants in cultural dialogue. Examples such as the Parliament building in Budapest, the Sydney Opera House, and the Guggenheim Museum in Bilbao illustrate how metaphors can reflect a nation's aspirations, its cultural characteristics, technological achievements, or historical connection to certain symbols.

In architecture, metaphors not only decorate but also serve as a bridge between the material world and the world of ideas, making political openness, cultural traditions, or technological progress visually tangible. They contribute to the creation of a unique artistic image, making buildings memorable and meaningful.

The conscious use of metaphors emphasizes the role of the architect not only as an engineer, but also as an artist and cultural figure who shapes the spatial environment in such a way that it tells stories, raises important questions and inspires reflection. Architectural projects that take into account metaphorical load and cultural contexts are able to create deeper and more layered interpretations, enriching the architectural landscape and making it more accessible and meaningful to humans.

References

1. Zaytseva Natalia Anatolyevna. "The Role of Metaphor in the Formation of an Architectural Object on the Example of the Work of the Bureau "Dominique Coulon Architectes"" *Architecture and Modern Information Technologies*, no. 3 (48), 2019, pp. 61-77.
2. Stepanov A.V. *Architecture and Psychology* / A.V. Stepanov, G.I. Ivanova, N.N. Nechaev. – Moscow: Stroiizdat, 1993. – Pp. 112-116
3. Viollet-le-Duc. *Discourses on Architecture*. – Vol. 2. – Moscow: All-Union Academy of Architecture, 1938. – Pp. 159-162.
4. Kashin V.V., and Musin D.Z. "Charles Peirce on the Representing Function of a Sign" *Bulletin of Orenburg State University*, no. 7 (113), 2010, pp. 127-132.